

KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE, AND PRACTICE OF CLINICAL-BASED RESEARCH AMONG NURSES OF SELECTED FEDERAL TEACHING HOSPITALS IN KADUNA METROPOLIS

**Idris Rakiya¹, Usman Zakari², Atiku Umar³, Abdullahi Fadimatu Manu¹, Yahaya Zainab Hassan⁴, Abubakar Faizah Sani⁸, Chuwang Nerat Darong⁸, Salami Fatima Onyinaname⁵, Umar Abdulhamid Ubandawaki², Ashumate Agbu Boniface⁶, Amina Muhammad Binni⁷, Aliyu Naziru Ayaro⁹*

¹College of Nursing Sciences, Ophthalmic Nursing Program, National Eye Center, Kaduna State, Nigeria

²Department of Nursing Sciences, Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto, Nigeria

³Department of Nursing Sciences, Iconic University, Sokoto, State, Nigeria

⁴Department of Maternal and Child Health, Faculty of Nursing and Allied Health Sciences, University of Abuja, FCT

⁵Fatima College of Nursing Sciences Sifawa, Sokoto, State

⁶Ophthalmic Unit, Taraba State Specialist Hospital, Jalingo, Nigeria

⁷Department of Nursing services, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital, Bauchi State, Nigeria

⁸Plateau State College of Nursing Science, Vom, Plateau State, Nigeria

⁹Federal Neuropsychiatric Hospital Kware, Sokoto, State

**Corresponding Author's Email ID & Phone Number: nanaruky419@gmail.com & +2347035581547*

ABSTRACT

Background: Research is a critical component of healthcare and essential for improving the quality and safety of patient care. Clinical nursing research, in particular, strengthens the evidence base for nursing practice. The availability of new treatment options or the improvement of existing treatments can only be achieved through clinical research. The success of clinical research depends on the educational levels and competence of clinical research team members, and good collaboration among them.

Assess the level of knowledge of clinically based research among nurses at selected Federal Teaching Hospitals in Kaduna Metropolis. Determine nurses' attitudes towards clinically based research and its publications among Nurses of selected Federal Teaching Hospitals in Kaduna Metropolis. Ascertain the views of nurses on the application of clinical-based research findings to practice among Nurses of selected Federal Teaching Hospitals in Kaduna Metropolis. A cross-sectional survey design was used, and data were collected with a structured questionnaire and analyzed using SPSS version 28.0. The result from the study found that the majority of the nurses demonstrate a substantial level of knowledge about clinically based research, they have a positive attitude towards clinically based research, and

the majority agree with the application of clinically based research findings in their practice. The conclusion drawn from these findings suggests that nurses demonstrate a substantial level of knowledge of clinically based research, a positive attitude, and a willingness to apply these findings in their practice.

Keywords: *nurses, knowledge, attitude, practice, clinical-based research, evidence-based practice*

INTRODUCTION

One of the most dynamic human disciplines is healthcare, and a lot of money is spent annually on high-quality, advanced research, resulting in exponential growth in the healthcare literature. Regularly, new and more effective medicines and procedures are established. One major objective behind all these efforts is to help doctors, nurses, and medical technicians provide patients with the best possible care and treatment (Alkhatib et al., 2021). Nursing is the largest, most diverse, and one of the most respected of all the health care professions. Clinical-based research provides a baseline for evidenced-base practice in nursing profession. Adequate knowledge and a positive attitude toward research are essential components of nursing practice; they are critical elements in improving the quality of health services and achieving excellence in patient care by providing research-based care. Nurses carry out research yearly which is a requirement for the award of registered nurse certificate in and also it is a requirement for the award of degree in nursing in Nigeria, yet studies are not published by Nigerian nurses, and those published are mostly nurse educators from the school and colleges of nurses as well as lecturers at the department of nursing at the university level. The application of the nursing research findings is one of the most important of developments in the nursing profession.

Approximately 27 million men and women make up the global nursing and midwifery

workforce. This accounts for nearly 50% of the global health workforce (World Health Organization (WHO), 2022). Africa accounts for 12.5% of the world's population. But it produces less than 1% of global research output. Sub-Saharan Africa has the lowest research capacity and output in the world. At this rate, the region's universities are unlikely ever to break into the top 10 or even 50 (Mutapi, 2021). The increased demand for healthcare, technological advancements, and the explosion of knowledge have necessitated a paradigm shift in nursing practice from one based on intuition and tradition to evidence-based practice (EBP). According to previous studies, EBP has not been widely utilized by most nurses working in clinical settings in Nigeria (Bankole et al., 2022). Previous studies have suggested that incorporating research findings into clinical practice brings about a high level of nursing care as well as improved patient outcomes, increased patient satisfaction, reduced hospital stay, efficient use of resources, elimination of unnecessary practices, and improved cost efficiency (Melnyk et al., 2014).

In a study conducted by Atakro et al. (2020) on the knowledge, attitudes, practices, and perceived barriers of evidence-based practice among registered nurses in a Ghanaian teaching hospital, the results of the study showed a generally high level of knowledge, attitudes, and practices of EBP among RNs in the teaching hospital. Although more than a third of participants did not know ab-

about databases that could be used in the search for evidence for practice. Similarly, studies in Africa have shown that a significant number of nurses had poor evidence-based practice utilization (Aynalem et al, 2021). Previous literatures indicate that Nigeria is making a paradigm shift towards becoming a hub for clinical trials in the next 10 years to come (Gimba et al, 2021).

CONCEPTUAL/THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

A conceptual framework represents a network of interlinked concepts that provides a structure for understanding a phenomenon and details the relationships among project components (Glover et al., 2020). This study is guided by the Knowledge-Attitude-Practice (KAP) model, which posits that an individual's knowledge influences their attitudes, and both shape subsequent practices. In nursing and health research, the KAP model is widely used to assess how knowledge and attitudes determine clinical behaviors. For example, Zhang et al. (2025) applied the KAP model to evaluate nurses' knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding nursing document quality control and reported significant improvement in KAP following targeted training. In the context of this study, the KAP framework helps explain how nurses' knowledge of clinical-based research may influence their attitudes toward research and affect their actual research practices, thereby identifying gaps and facilitators in research participation among nurses in selected federal teaching hospitals in Kaduna metropolis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS RESEACH DESIGN

A cross-sectional descriptive survey design was used to assess the level of knowledge and practice of clinical based research among nurses of selected federal teaching hospitals in Kaduna metropolis.

TARGET POPULATION

The target population was nurses from the National Eye Center, Kaduna, and the Federal Neuropsychiatry Barnawa, Kaduna.

SAMPLE SIZE DETERMINATION

The sample size was determined using Yamane's (1967) simplified formula for finite populations, where $N =$ population size (251) and a margin of error (e) of 5%. The calculated sample size was 154. Inclusion criteria included all nurses working at the National Eye Centre and the Federal Neuropsychiatric Hospital, Barnawa, Kaduna.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

A proportionate stratified sampling technique was employed to determine the number of questionnaires assigned to each hospital based on their respective population sizes. This ensured that participants from both facilities were fairly represented in the study. The total population across the two hospitals was 251. Consequently, 60 questionnaires were allocated to the National Eye Centre (NEC), which had a population of 97, while 94 questionnaires were allocated to the Federal Neuropsychiatric Hospital (FNP), with a population of 154, making a total of 154 questionnaires distributed. After determining the proportionate allocation, a convenience sampling technique was used in administering the questionnaires. This approach enabled the researcher to recruit

respondents who were available and willing to participate at the time of data collection.

INSTRUMENT FOR DATA COLLECTION

The researcher used an adapted questionnaire, which was created after completion of a focused literature review. A well-structured questionnaire adapted from (Abdullahi, 2023), (Bamila & Rani, 2021), and (Tumilara & Oluwatosin, 2021) was modified to suit the study objectives.

METHOD FOR DATA ANALYSIS

The data were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 28.0. Descriptive statistical tools such as frequency, percentages, mean, and standard deviation were used to summarize the data.

VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY

To measure the validity of the instrument, the questionnaire was reviewed by the project supervisor. The internal consistency of the questionnaire was assessed using Cronbach's alpha coefficient, yielding a value of 0.7 for items assessing knowledge, 0.8 for items assessing attitudes, and 0.7 for items assessing nurses' views towards the application of clinical based research.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

The researcher obtained an introductory letter from the secretary of the research committee of the School of Post Basic Ophthalmic Nursing, National Eye Center, Kaduna, which was given to the DDNS/HOD nursing services of National Eye Center and Federal Neuro-Psychiatric Hospital, Barnawa, Kaduna, Nigeria, and oral consent from the respondents was obtained. Full explanation of the study was offered to the respondents before distributi-

ng the questionnaires to them, and also their norms and culture were respected. All the information received from the respondents was strictly kept under utmost confidentiality.

RESULTS

3.1 Distribution of Sample According to Socio-Demographic Data (N=150)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage(%)
Age as at last birthday		
Below 20	4	2.70
21-29	67	44.70
31-39	51	34.00
49 and above	28	18.70
Gender		
Male	43	28.70
Female	107	71.30
Educational qualifications		
Diploma	92	61.30
BNSc	52	34.70
MSc	6	4.00
PhD	0	0
Rank		
NO II	50	33.30
NO I	38	25.30
SNO	22	14.70
PNO	9	6.00
ACNO	17	11.30
CNO	3	2.00
ADNS	8	5.30
DDNS	3	2.00
Institution		
NEC	60	40.00
FNPH	90	60.00
Years of experience		
Less than 1 year	34	22.70
1-5 years	31	20.70
6-10 years	66	44.00
10 years and above	29	19.30

Table 3.1 above shows that the majority of the nurses are within the age range of 21-29 with a percentage of 44.7% (67) which is followed closely by those within the age range of 30-39 with a percentage of 34% (51), 18.70% (28) are within the age range of 40 years and above and the least being those below 20 years with a percentage of 2.70% (4). The majority of the nurses were females with a frequency of 107(71.30%) and males 43(28.70%). The majority of the nurses are diploma holders with a percentage of 61.30% (92), 34.70% (52), and 4% (6) are masters holders and none has a PhD. The majority of the nurses are Nursing officer II with a percentage of 33.30% (50), 25.30% (38) are Nursing Officer I, 14.70% (22) are Senior Nursing Officers, 11.30% (17) are Assistant Chief Nursing Officers, 6.00% (9) are Principal Nursing Officers, 5.30% (8) are Assistant Director of Nursing Services and 2.00% (3) are the percentage for both Chief Nursing Officer and Deputy Director of Nursing Services. Majority of the respondents are from Federal Neuropsychiatric Hospital, Barnawa, Kaduna, with a percentage of 60.00 % (90) and 40.00% (60) of the nurses are from National Eye Center Kaduna. The majority of the nurses have 6-10 years of working experience with, a frequency of 66(44.00%), 22.70% (34) have less than 1 year working experience, 20.70% (31) and the least being 10 years and above working experience, with a percentage of 19.30% (29)

Table 3.2 Level of Knowledge about clinical research among nurses

Statements	Yes(F)	Yes(%)	No(F)	No(%)
Have you heard of the speciality clinical nursing research?	131	87.30	18	12.70

Can you conduct a scientific research or clinical based research?	135	90.00	15	10.00
Have you received any formal education or training on clinical based research?	113	75.30	37	24.70
Can you write references or citation?	112	74.70	38	25.30
Can you write a manuscript?	94	62.70	56	37.30
Can you navigate the internet to extract literature review?	129	86.00	21	14.00
Do you believe there are many gaps in current nursing education curricula regarding the teaching of clinical based research concept and skills?	120	80.00	30	20.00

Table 3.2 above shows that 87.30% of the nurses have heard of specialty clinical research nursing, while 12.70% have not. 90.00% know how to conduct scientific research or clinical-based research, while 10.00% cannot. 75.30% have received formal education or training on clinical-based research

ch, while 24.70% have not. 74.70% can write references or citation while 25.30% cannot, 62.70% can write a manuscript while 37.30% cannot, 86.00% can navigate the internet to extract literature review while 14.00% cannot, 80.00% believes that there are gaps in the current nursing education curricula regarding the teaching of clinical based research concept and skills while 20.00% believes there is no gap. From the results above, this implies that the majority of the nurses of Federal Neuropsychiatric Hospital, Barnawa, Kaduna, and National Eye Center, Kaduna, demonstrate a substantial level of knowledge about clinically based research.

The Likert scale was used to present the data in a table. Using a Likert scale of 5, the decision mean is

$$DM = EX/N$$

Decision mean = sum of all items / total number of items / sets

$$DM = 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 / 5$$

$$DM = 3.0$$

Therefore, any mean of 3.0 and above the decision mean is considered agreed while any other less than a decision mean of 3.0 is considered disagreed.

Table 3.3 Attitudes of nurses towards clinical based research

Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation
Clinical based research is useful to nursing and enhances the standard of patient care	4.63	0.79
I love and enjoys carrying research	4.27	0.86
I have participated in clinical based research	3.84	1.09
Research is difficult and complicated	2.92	1.36
Research in general makes me anxious and	2.87	1.28

nervous	2.48	1.31
Research is stressful and I lack confidence in carrying it out		
Aggregate Mean	3.50	

Table 3.3 shows the mean score for each item is 4.63, 4.27, 4.3, 3.84, 2.92, 2.87, and 2.48, respectively. Therefore, all items that scored ≥ 3.0 were accepted, and those below 3.0 were rejected, since the aggregate mean is 3.50, and it is greater than 3.0, this suggests that the majority of the nurses have a positive attitude towards clinically based research.

Table 3.4 Nurses View on the Application of Clinical Based Research Finding to Practice

Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation
Staff should base their decisions on the latest clinical nursing research findings	4.43	0.68
Research is useful to justify why decisions are made in practice	4.31	0.89
Management provide protocol on how to apply research findings	3.99	1.13
I automatically use clinical nursing research in my every day work	3.79	1.11
It is easy to change practice so that it reflects research findings	3.70	1.15
Aggregate Mean	4.04	

Table 3.4 shows Nurses' views on the Application of clinical-based research findings to practice; the mean scores for each item are 4.43, 4.31, 3.99, 3.79, and 3.70, respectively. An aggregate mean of 4.04 was obtained, which is greater than the decision mean of 3.0. This indicates that the majority of nurses agree with the application of clinical-based research findings in their practice.

DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS

Socio-Demographic Data

Findings of the study reveal that the majority of nurses are within the age range of 21–29 years, which is slightly lower than the 30.6 ± 6.7 years reported by Kao et al. (2019) in their study on nurses' knowledge and attitudes toward clinical trials in Taiwan, and also lower than the 34.6 ± 7.4 years reported by Aksoy et al. (2018) in their study on nurses' knowledge, attitudes, and opinions toward clinical research in a university hospital in Turkey. The majority of nurses were female, which is similar to the study conducted by Abdullahi (2023) on the assessment of nurses' knowledge and attitudes toward clinical nursing research and its application to practice, where the researcher reported that most participants were female. Most nurses were diploma holders, having attended a school of nursing and obtained a license as registered nurses (RN). This finding contrasts with that of Aksoy et al. (2018), which reported that most nurses held bachelor's degrees. Similarly, the results differ from the study conducted at Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, by Abdullahi (2023), where more than half of the nurses were degree holders. The majority of nurses in the current study were Nursing Officer II, which contrasts with Abdullahi (2023), who reported that most nurses were Senior Nursing Officers. Most nurses had 6–10 years of work experience. This is similar to Aksoy et al. (2018), who found that the majority of nurses had 1–9 years of clinical experience.

Level of Knowledge about Clinical-Based Research

The findings of this study indicate that most nurses possess a high level of knowledge regarding clinical-based research.

These findings are consistent with those of Abdullahi (2023), who conducted a study among nurses at the Ahmadu Bello University Teaching Hospital (ABUTH), Shika, Zaria, Kaduna State, Nigeria, and reported that the majority of nurses demonstrated strong knowledge of clinical nursing research and its application to practice. These results suggest that nurses' awareness of clinical research principles can be significantly enhanced through professional training and exposure to research activities.

Attitudes of Nurses towards Clinical-Based Research and Its Publications

The study suggests that the majority of nurses have a positive attitude toward clinical-based research. This aligns with the study conducted by Bankole et al. (2022) in a Federal Teaching Hospital in Edo State, Nigeria, which explored nurses' perceptions and utilization of evidence-based practice. Their findings revealed that nurses generally have a positive attitude toward integrating research findings into clinical practice, with a mean score of 2.32 ± 0.88 , supporting the notion that nurses recognize the value of research in clinical decision-making. In contrast, Qureshi et al. (2019) reported that nurses at a tertiary care hospital in Lahore, Pakistan, exhibited less positive attitudes toward research, largely due to a lack of awareness, insufficient supportive environment, and heavy workloads. This comparison highlights the influence of context and institutional support on nurses' attitudes toward clinical-based research.

Views of Nurses on the Application of Clinical-Based Research Findings to Practice

The results of this study indicate that the majority of nurses agree with applying clinically based research findings in their practice. This aligns with the findings of

Nkeiruka et al. (2024) in children's wards at tertiary health institutions in Anambra State, Nigeria, where 82.7% of nurses demonstrated good knowledge of evidence-based practice. Despite this strong knowledge base, 53.5% of nurses reported a negative attitude toward evidence-based practice, and 70.1% exhibited poor implementation of research findings. Similarly, Dagne and Tebeje (2021) in South Gondar Zone public hospitals, Ethiopia, reported that while some nurses and midwives actively utilized research findings in practice, others did not integrate research evidence into their clinical work. These studies highlight that although nurses generally recognize the importance of clinical-based research, the actual application of research findings may vary depending on context, individual experience, and institutional support.

CONCLUSION

Findings suggest that nurses demonstrate a substantial level of knowledge of clinically based research, a positive attitude, and a willingness to apply these findings in their practice.

RECOMMENDATION

Although nurses exhibit a considerable level of knowledge regarding clinical-based research, there is a need to strengthen institutional support to enhance research output. The research committee should advocate for management to allocate adequate resources for research activities and provide study or research leave for nurses who intend to engage in scholarly work. Such support will help promote a more robust culture of clinical-based research among Nigerian nurses.

LIMITATION

The study faced several limitations, including gaps in the existing literature rela-

ted to the topic and financial constraints that prevented the use of a larger sample size. Time limitations also affected the depth of data collection and analysis; initially, the use of an electronic questionnaire yielded low responses, prompting a shift to printed questionnaires, which increased costs. Additionally, distance posed logistical challenges during the research process.

SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

This study investigated the knowledge, attitude, and practice of clinical-based research among nurses in selected Federal Teaching Hospitals within Kaduna Metropolis. Future research should focus on identifying effective strategies for translating research findings into routine clinical practice, as well as exploring the factors that influence nurses' engagement in clinical-based research. Such studies will help strengthen the integration of evidence-based practice within the nursing profession.

REFERENCES

- Abdullahi, Z. Z. (2023). Assessment of knowledge and attitude of nurses towards clinical nursing research and its application to nursing practice. ResearchGate. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17938.43209>
- Aksoy Bulut, H., Arici, M. A., Ucku, R., & Gelal, A. (2018). Nurses' knowledge, attitudes and opinions towards clinical research: A cross-sectional study in a university hospital. *Journal of Basic and Clinical Health Sciences*, 2, 38–44. <https://doi.org/10.30621/jbachs.2018.403>
- Alkhatib, A. H., Ibrahim, E. A., Ameenuddin, M., & Ibrahim, I. A. (2021). Nurses' knowledge, perception, and attitude towards evidence-based practice at King Abdullah Medical City-Saudi Arabia. *American Journal of Nursing Research*, 9(1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.12691/ajnr-9-1-1>
- Atakro, C. A., Akuoko, C. P., Aboagye, J. S., Blay, A. A., Addo, S. B., Sallah, R., Gyamera Sarpong, Y., Atakro, A., Adatar, P., Agyare, D. F., Amoa-Gyarteng, K. G., Garti, I., Menlah, A., Ansong, I. K., & Boni, G. S. (2020). Knowledge, attitudes, practices and perceived barriers of evidence-based practice among registered nurses in a Ghanaian teaching hospital. *International Journal of Africa Nursing Sciences*, 12, 100204. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijans.2020.100204>
- Aynalem, Z. B., Yazew, K. G., & Gebrie, M. H. (2021). Evidence-based practice utilization and associated factors among nurses working in Amhara Region Referral Hospitals, Ethiopia. *PLOS ONE*, 16(3), e0248834. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0248834>
- Bamila, N., & Rani, T. J. (2021). Knowledge and attitude of nursing students towards research. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology (IJISRT)*, 6(12), 20–28. <https://doi.org/10.9790/3008-1602042028>
- Bankole, S. O., Nwankwo, C. U., Brotobor, D., & Afonne, J. A. (2022). Knowledge, attitude, and utilization of evidence-based practice among nurses in tertiary hospitals. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 13(3), 63–72. <https://wjarr.com/sites/default/files/WJARR-2022-0140.pdf>
- Dagne, A. H., & Tebeje, H. D. (2021). Research utilization in clinical practice: The experience of nurses and midwives working in public hospitals. *Reproductive Health*, 18(1), 62. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12978-021-01095-x>
- Gimba, S. N., Nanda, A., Sabo, H., & Lawan, S. (2021). Conducting global clinical trial in Nigeria: Issues, challenges and prospects. *IOSR Journal of Pharmacy and Biological Sciences (IOSR-JPBS)*, 16(2, Ser. IV), 20–28. <https://doi.org/10.9790/3008-1602042028>
- Glover, R. E., van Schalkwyk, M. C., Akl, E. A., Kristjansson, E., Lotfi, T., Petkovic, J., Petticrew, M. P., Pottie, K., Tugwell, P., & Welch, V. (2020). A framework for identifying and mitigating the equity harms of COVID-19 policy interventions. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, 128, 35–48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2020.06.004>
- Melnyk, B. M., Gallagher-Ford, L., Long, L. E., & Fineout-Overholt, E. (2014). The establishment of evidence-based practice competencies for practicing registered nurses and advanced practice nurses in real-world clinical settings: Proficiencies to improve healthcare quality, reliability, patient outcomes, and costs. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*, 11(1), 5–15. <https://doi.org/10.1111/wvn.12021>
-

- Mutapi, F. (2021). Africa needs to speed up research excellence: Here's how. The Conversation. Retrieved from <https://theconversation.com/africa-needs-to-speed-up-research-excellence-heres-how-169552>
- Nkeiruka, J. J., Agbapuwu, E. N., & Yarhere, I. (2024). Knowledge, attitude and practice of evidence-based nursing among nurses in children's ward at tertiary health institutions in Anambra State, Nigeria. *African Journal of Health, Nursing and Midwifery*, 7(2), 115–140. <https://doi.org/10.52589/AJHNM-AR1OMDJE>
- Qureshi, H., Firdos, U., Hussain, M., Afzal, M., & Gilani, S. A. (2019). Knowledge and attitude of nurses toward research at a tertiary care hospital Lahore. *International Journal of Graduate Research Review*, 5(1), 31–38. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/333816533_Knowledge_and_Attitude_of_Nurses_toward_Research_at_a_Tertiary_Care_Hospital_Lahore
- Tumilara, B. A., & Oluwatosin, G. (2021). Nursing and midwifery students' attitudes towards research: A descriptive study. *Asian Journal of Nursing Education and Research*, 11(3), 375–380. <https://doi.org/10.52711/2349-2996.2021.00090>
- World Health Organization. (2022). Global strategic directions for nursing and midwifery 2021–2025. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240033863>
- Zhang, L., Chen, R., Zhong, X., Xu, M., Sun, Y., & Yao, Q. (2025). Nurses' knowledge-attitude-practice of the importance of quality control of nursing documents and the influence of intensive training: A study from a tertiary hospital in China. *BMC Medical Education*, 25, Article 604. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-025-07168-w>